

Original Research

Impact of Non-Tariff Barriers on Maize Trade Volume at the Manyovu Border: Evidence from Tanzania-Burundi Cross-Border Traders Using Regression Analysis

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Abstract

The recent studies on the maize export through the Tanzania-Burundi border reveals a significant 50% decline in trade volume in 2023. This study analyzed the Impact of Non-Tariff Barriers on maize trade volume at the Manyovu Border focusing from Tanzania-Burundi Cross-Border Trade. Using a cross-sectional design with data from 150 respondents and multiple regression analysis, the study analysed the impact of various NTBs on maize trade. The key findings indicated that costs for soliciting export permits reduced volume of maize trade by 23% and business license costs to a 17% decline in trade. Similarly, road blocks and weighing bridge reduced the maize trade volume by 15% and 19% respectively. These results highlight how NTBs increases transaction cost, hindering efficient of cross-border maize trade. The study recommends, Ministry of Agriculture and Ministry Industry and Trade prioritize initiatives to reduce NTBs, such as digitalization of customs procedures, fully implementing the One-Stop Center and enforcing the East African Community's Elimination of Non-Tariff Barriers Act. Such initiatives are critical in lowering business transaction costs for traders and transporters, thus facilitating smoother and more efficient trade between the two countries. This study contributes to the growing body of evidence on NTBs effect in less developed countries.

Keywords: Burundi, Manyovu Boarder, NTBs, Regression analysis, Tanzania, Transaction costs.

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Introduction

Global exporters and importers face a multitude of administrative obstacles and extended customs processes at various border points in many developing nations, which are regarded as significant non-tariff barriers to cross-border trade. In Africa, the primary cross-border food staples traded among African and East African countries is maize and maize flour (FAO, 2023; UN COMTRADE, 2023). In this respect, maize is a vital crop for global food security, supporting both human and livestock diets while also supplying essential raw materials for biofuel production (FAOSTAT, 2021; Nyaligwa et al., 2017). The estimated value of cross-border trade in East Africa stands at USD 1.76 billion, with 40% of this figure linked to the trade of agricultural products (East Africa Cross-Border Trade Bulletin, 2022; George, 2021; Nanjira, 2015). Furthermore, maize trade in EAC experienced a 16% decrease from USD 180,428 thousands in 2023 to 152,196 thousand in the year 2024 (UN COMTRADE STAT, 2025). Moreover, decline in maize price reduced the EAC trade to 252,000 MT, equivalent to 55% decrease compared to the same quarter in 2023 (FEWS NET, 2024).

Study by Santeramo and Lamonaca (2019) indicate that the imposition of non-tariff barriers (NTBs) is significantly linked to a decrease in staple food cross-border trade in Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). This implies that that the arbitrary imposition of non-tariff barriers by governments may distort cross-border trade within the East African Community. Domestic maize production in Tanzania, Kenya, Uganda, Burundi, and Rwanda accounts for more than 50% of the national grain supply (FEWS NET, 2023). While, 90% of the rural population in the majority of EAC member countries consumes it (Kitole et al., 2023; Madara & Tsyokor, 2022). So, promoting enter regional trade could contribute much to food security among EAC members.

In the 2023/2024 period, East Africa was projected to achieve a net surplus of 1,700,000 MT in maize production. The surplus was anticipated to enhance cross-border trade between EAC member countries and the global market. Contrary, the East Africa Cross-border Trade Bulletin (2023) reported a decline in the share of maize cross-border trade within the EAC, decreasing from 48 percent to 31 percent in 2023. Saad (2021) and EAC (2020) identify high transaction costs, including non-tariff barriers (NTBs), as significant factors contributing to the low rate of cross-border trade in Africa and the East African Community (EAC). This gives the implication that, cross border trade like that of maize diminishes with the application of policies which associated with trade barriers such as NTBs. Maize ranks as a leading agricultural export from Tanzania to neighboring countries, with beans and rice following in significance (Vicent and Njong, 2021; Baya, 2019).

Moreover, Tanzania is a main maize producer among the EAC member countries, with an estimated production of 6.1 Metric tons (MT) in 2022, 12 MT in 2024, and projected to increase to 18 MT in 2025/2026 (MoA, 2025; USDA, 2023). The increase in maize production has been attributed by the current government initiatives in provision of input subsidies program which included fertilizers and certified seeds (MoA, 2025). In this respective, Tanzania will remain the primary supplier of maize to Burundi, Rwanda, South Sudan, and Kenya, as these nations typically face low maize production (FEWS NET, 2022).

Despite the increase in maize production, data from UN COMTRADE STAT (2025, EAC, 2022) reported a decline in the value of maize exports from Tanzania to Burundi from USD 2,081 thousands in 2022 to USD 589 thousands in 2024. These supports the previous reported decrease of 50% by Trade Economics (2022) in the year 2021. Similarly, WFP (2023) indicated that the exportable surplus of maize in Tanzania is projected to be 20% below the average for the 2022/2023 season. The decline in the bilateral maize trade between the two country could be linked with increase transaction costs in moving the product. Generally, it is important to recognize that barriers to agricultural cross-border trade contribute to heightened food insecurity and malnutrition among low-income individuals in East African Community member states.

TCCIA-Kigoma (2022) reports that over 60% of maize cross-border trade between Tanzania and Burundi occurs at the Manyovu border in the Kigoma region. Cross-border traders at the Manyovu border face significant challenges due to various non-tariff barriers, raising concerns among policymakers and development partners, including AGRA and USAID. TCCIA (2022) noted that, bureaucratic administrative requirements for inter-regional trade impede economic growth by restricting access to regional markets among member countries. Furthermore, the amount of maize exported at the Manyovu border has continued to fall, despite significant progress achieved by the EAC governments in lowering NTBs to promote seamless cross-border trade (George, 2021; Okute, 2017). However, as evidenced by the 35% drop in maize exports to Burundi from USD 1.84 million in 2020 to USD 1.21 million in 2021. This decrease could be linked to NTBs imposed arbitrary by governments which impact the amount of maize trade between Tanzania and Burundi.

Previous research on non-tariff barriers (NTBs) and maize trade in Tanzania, such as those of Gabagambi (2013) and Mnondwa et al. (2024) has predominantly focused on domestic market dynamics. While a few numbers of studies have explored the impact of NTBs on cross-border maize trade but concentrated to neighboring countries like Kenya and Rwanda (Mkuna, 2014; Masinde, 2015; George, 2021; Vicent & Njong, 2021), there remains a significant gap in understanding how NTBs affect trade between Tanzania and Burundi. This gap is particularly evident at the Manyovu border, where maize trade volumes have experienced a sharp decline, from USD 2.08 million in 2022 to USD 589 thousand in 2024 (UN COMTRADE STAT, 2025). This persistent decrease, despite regional policy efforts such as the implementation of the Common External Tariff (CET) Protocol, raises critical questions about the underlying trade constraints. Unlike to previous studies, this study examined the effect of NTBs on maize trade volume focusing to Tanzania-Burundi at the Manyovu border using primary trader's data. To reach the conclusion, the study is operating under the hypothesis that transaction costs associated with NTBs have a negative impact on maize trade performance.

The findings of this study provide timely and actionable insights for policymakers, offering evidence to inform the development of targeted strategies aimed at reducing NTBs and enhancing cross-border maize trade between Tanzania and Burundi. By addressing these barriers, regional stakeholders can foster more efficient trade flows, improve market access, and support agricultural livelihoods across the border in EAC.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Similar to Liang (2020), the theoretical background of this study is framed based on the Transaction Cost Theory and the Theory of Government Intervention.

Theory of Transaction Costs

Transaction Cost Economics (TCE), first introduced by Coase (1937) and later expanded by Williamson (1979), provides a foundational framework for understanding the structure and behavior of firms and markets under information asymmetric. At its core, TCE posits that economic exchanges are not governed solely by price mechanisms but are significantly influenced by transaction costs which includes costs of searching for information, negotiating contracts, monitoring compliance, and enforcing agreements (Key et al., 2000; Sebatta et al., 2014). These costs become particularly salient in environments characterized by information asymmetry, where one party possesses more or better information than the other, leading to inefficiencies and potential exploitation.

The report by Ozekhome and Braimah (2023), demonstrate that information asymmetry exacerbates transaction costs, especially in developing and emerging markets where market transparency is limited and regulatory oversight is weak. In the work of Makhura et al. (2001) and Makindara (2012) the transaction costs are the expenses associated with moving goods and services from one activity to another. Thus, high transaction costs resulted from protection policy like NTBs deter formal market participation. In such contexts, traders and firms often seek alternative channels that offer lower costs and fewer bureaucratic hurdles in trade exchange. This theory on the other hand, views businesses or traders as actors that aim to minimize transaction costs (Makhura et al., 2001). This suggests that businesses and traders will be open to participating in a trade, which may result in lower transaction costs for them.

The above argument was supported by Williamson (1979) who argued that non-tariff barriers (NTBs) and other formal trade restrictions discourage traders' participation in regulated markets, pushing them toward informal systems where contract enforcement is flexible, monitoring is minimal, and negotiation is more adaptive. This is supported by Wiseman (2023), who found that informal traders at the Kenya-Uganda border responded positively to improved access to price and tariff information, leading to increased profits and partial formalization of trade. Similarly, maize traders at the Manyovu border are considered to have the same objectives of minimizing the transaction cost resulting from NTBs. The study by Bwalya et.al (2013) noted that, in the situation where costs of exchange are caused by NTBs, the theory of Transaction cost can help in explaining how the regulatory and barriers can increase transaction costs in moving goods/service in Less Developed Countries (LCD) like Tanzania. It is under this context; the theory was considered to be suitable in this study to explain the impact of NTBs on maize exporters at Manyovu border in Tanzania.

Generally, TCE provides a robust lens for analyzing how market actors navigate environments with high transaction costs and information asymmetry. The shift toward informal channels is not merely a reaction to regulatory constraints but a calculated move to optimize efficiency. Recent literature affirms that reducing information frictions and

improving institutional support can lower transaction costs and encourage formalization, enhancing overall market performance.

Moreover, Makhura et al. (2001) and Bwalya et al. (2013) contended that the theory of transaction costs is the appropriate method for analyzing agricultural markets in developing nations like Tanzania and Burundi, where markets are imperfect (market failure), in which it difficult to capture the effects of transaction costs on market exchange. Conventional neoclassical economics is unable to explain the prevalence of market failure and incomplete market information in developing nations due to higher transaction costs and information asymmetries; instead, an institutional analysis is necessary, with a focus on the application of transaction costs theory (Eggertson, 1990; Key et al., 2000). Because the theory of transaction costs acknowledges that many commercial interactions might be categorized as imperfect or asymmetric, it was chosen to serve as the foundation for the claims in this paper.

Similar to this, the government's intervention on staple food crops like maize through NTB strategies has resulted in market failures that have increased transaction costs in the cross-border trade of maize between Tanzania and Burundi. These market failures have an impact on the exportation of maize through the Manyovu border (TCCIA, 2022). These costs are linked to export prohibitions, lengthy and onerous customs procedures, bureaucratic in acquiring administrative requirements, the presence of numerous checkpoints, and high transportation costs because of security concerns (Bwalya et al., 2013). Since NTBs are typically enforced by the government as preventative measures, the Theory of Government Intervention was taken into consideration as a supplement to the TOT. To raise awareness of food insecurity, governments typically impose NTBs on the exchange of staple food crops, particularly during times of food scarcity. Similar to this, the government should eradicate NTBs as a trade facilitation tactic meant to revive international trade.

Theory of Government Intervention

The theory of Government Intervention was first proposed by Keynes in 1936 and is extensively applied in international trade. Keynes (1936) posits that governments ought to employ monetary and fiscal policies to intervene and stimulate economic demand. Governments play crucial roles in market intervention when market participants are unable to address issues of monopoly and externalities due to a lack of information (Stiglitz, 1977). Greenwald and Stiglitz (1986) argued that government intervention on market will lead to information asymmetric among market actors (market imperfection). This may result into increases transaction costs and price fluctuations imposing large costs on exporters and importers (Arnott et al., 1994). Under such situation, the markets are not following the Pareto efficiency (perfect), so will associated with more information searching costs. As a way of overcoming such condition, many governments particularly in developing countries introduces various policies and regulations. The formulated policies and guidelines are thought to enhance cross-border trade through reduced NTBs in form of administrative and customs procedures. In reality, these interventions had resulted into the decrease in cross border trade in many economic integrations. In support to this argument, Santeramo and Lamonaca (2019) note that the arbitrary imposition of non-tariff barriers (NTBs) by governments is significantly linked to a decrease in staple

food cross-border trade in Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The use of this theory in the current study will help in explaining the impact of NTBs imposed by EAC member countries such as Tanzania and Burundi in maize trade.

Conceptual Framework of the study

Figure 1 present the conceptual framework for this study showing the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. It was hypothesised that, the imposition of NTBs in form of administrative procedures, custom procedures and transit procedures will increase the transaction costs and thus discourage the maize trade across the Manyovu border. The administrative procedures were operationalized through export permit; business license and compliance certificates as reported by Masinde (2015) whereas custom procedures were related to issues such as entry declaration; unloading and examination; and placing goods under a customs procedure (Thush, 2018). On the other, transit procedures were operationalized by identifying issues such as road blocks, police check points and weighbridges (Mnondwa et al. (2024; Anyona, 2018).

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework

Research Methods

Research Approach and Design

This study utilized a cross-sectional design, employing a survey method in which participants responded to self-administered questionnaires at a single point in time. This study was conducted at the Manyovu border in Kigoma region. The Manyovu border was chosen for this study due to its significance as a transport and trade route facilitating maize cross-border trade between Tanzania and Burundi. TCCIA-Kigoma (2022) reports that over 60% of maize cross-border trade between Tanzania and Burundi occurs at the Manyovu border in the Kigoma region. Kigoma ranks as the second largest maize producer in Tanzania, with scale trader, especially women, contributing to 80% of the production (SAKiRP, 2022). Burundi is regarded as a promising export market for maize farmers in Kigoma (AGRA, 2020). Consequently, the Manyovu border served as an optimal location to examine the effects of non-tariff barriers on the volume of maize cross-border trade.

Sample Size and Sampling Methods

A sample of 150 respondents was drawn from a target population of 240 stakeholders (Registered maize Traders and Transporters) within the study's sampling frame, deemed optimal for fulfilling the study's aims and objectives. The list of traders and transporter were obtained from TCCIA- Kigoma, Kigoma regional trade office and TRA office at Manyovu Border. The study only involved registered traders and not considered informal traders because it was intended to evaluate the contribution of transactions costs resulted from formal cross border procedures such Administration procedure, Transit and Custom procedures which are mostly faced by register traders (George, 2021 and Nanjira, 20215).

A sample size was calculated using Yamane's Formula (Yamane, 1967), chosen for its flexibility in determining sample sizes across various levels of precision and confidence intervals. The study's sample size was determined as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where, n = sample size, N = population size, e = the margin error

Therefore, under this study, N=240, e=5%.

$$n = \frac{240}{1 + 240(0.05)^2} = 150$$

To select the respondents, a stratified sampling technique was used to categorize the population into 2 strata (Traders and Transporter) whereby a Probability Proportional to Size (PPS) was used to select the sample size from strata. The application of stratified sampling is based on its ability of ensuring that every stratum is adequately represented (Kothari, 2013 and Saunders *et al.* 2023) To select the respondents, a proportional simple random sampling technique was used to obtain the required number from the list of traders and transporters from each stratum. The random selection of the respondents

ensured an equal chance for respondents who were selected for the study, hence helping to reduce bias in sample selection. Table 1 below shows the distribution of the sample size.

Table 1: Sample size distribution

Group	Population	Computation	Sample Size
Traders	160	$160/240 * 150 = 100$	100
Transporters	80	$80/240 * 150 = 50$	50
Total	240		150

Data Collection Methods

This study involved the collection of both primary and secondary data. Data were collected from maize cross-border traders and transporters at the Manyovu border using a self-administered questionnaire. Traders and transporters provided data on the transfer costs related to various NTBs they face along the trade exchange across the border of Manyovu. Consistent with the work of Henson and Loader (2001) and Bowen (2018), the questionnaire utilized both a closed-ended and open format to widen the participation of respondents. Additionally, Likert questions were designed to improve comprehension and minimize confusion for respondents when reading and answering the questions. Questionnaires were translated in the Kiswahili a local language in Tanzania to facilitate the understanding of the meaning.

Additionally, an observational method was employed to monitor and document significant issues about non-tariff barriers at the Manyovu border in the Kigoma region. This entailed the observation of administrative, customs, and transit procedures executed by maize traders and transporters at the border, as well as the examination of underlying issues, including corruption. Furthermore, the observation involved capturing photographs of the events as they occurred to acquire concrete evidence and facilitate the analysis of the recorded observations. The observation method allowed the researcher to supplement primary data gathered from the questionnaire, thereby improving the validity of the study's data.

Sample size for Key informant is based on the data saturation point-the point when no new themes emerge. Studies by Morse (2000) and Suri (2011) shows that for small-scale or local studies, a sample of 10 to 15 key informants is generally sufficient, whereas regional studies typically require 20 to 30 key informants. As this study falls within the small-scale category, 10 Key Informants were involved and interviewed. The participants included representatives from the TRA, TCCIA-private Apex, customs officers, the Kigoma trade office, and Ward leaders. These interviews were employed for data triangulation to enrich and supplement the information collected.

Conversely, secondary data were obtained through a documentary review, in which the researcher examined existing literature to enhance the primary data. A variety of literature concerning non-tariff barriers and trade was examined and analyzed. The researcher conducted a review of pertinent documents concerning maize export market

trends in Tanzania and Burundi, highlighting production and processing, sales and imports, exports, revenues, consumption patterns, and demand trends.

Data analysis and Analytical Models

The Multiple regression model was utilized to analyze the relationship between non-tariff barriers and the volume of maize cross-border trade. The dependent variable was the transformed volume of maize, while the independent variables included all transformed customs-related NTBs variables. Karugia et al. (2009) and Minot (2010) categorize non-tariff barriers (NTBs) into three types: administrative requirements, customs procedures, and transit procedures. The examination of the impact of non-tariff barriers on maize trade at the Manyovu border was structured around three principal categories. Moreover, Table 2 presents the measurements and expected direction of effect for dependent variables as used in the results section.

Table 2: Operationalization and measurement of variables

Variables	Measurement	Effect
Average Volume of Maize Exported by Traders (Dependent)	Metric Ton (MT)	
<i>Independent Variables</i>		
Export Permit	Money paid (TZS)/Time taken to secure the permit (HRS)	(-)
Business Licensing	Money paid (TZS)/Time (HRS)	(-)
Compliance Certificates	Money paid (TZS)/Time (HRS)	(-)
Entry Declaration	(Time (HRS)/Costs (TZS)	(-)
Unloading and Examination	Time (HRS) and Costs (TZS)	(-)
Placing goods under customs	Storage Costs (TZS/Day)	(-)
Road Blocks	Money paid (TZS)/Time (HRS)	(-)
Weighing Bridges	Money paid / Time taken (HRS)	(-)
Police Checkpoints	Money paid to cross the point (TZS)	(-)

Source: Researcher hypotheses based on NTBs Literatures (Karugia et al. 2011; Bwalya et al. 2013).

The study evaluates the impact of administrative procedures on maize trade volume by analyzing three primary components of non-tariff barriers (NTBs): export permit procedures, business licenses, and compliance certificates, which are treated as independent variables. NTBs were measured in amount of money paid (TZS) and time taken (HRS) to overcome the barrier by traders and transporters. Value of money (TZS) spent by traders and transporters on accommodation and meals were used as proximal to the time wasted (HRS) at weighing bridges, road blocks and at the border, and were included in the analysis. The annual average volume of maize exported cross the border from individual trader measured as aggregate in Metric Tons (MT) at Manyovu was considered a dependent variable for this objective. Primary data were validated with the

available data at the TCCIA and TRA offices at Manyovu border to improve their reliability.

In this respect, the regression model was expressed in the following equation:

$$MT = \beta_1 + \beta_2EP + \beta_3BL + \beta_4CoC + \beta_5Ee + \beta_6Ue + \beta_7Pg + \beta_8RB + \beta_9WB + \beta_{10}PC + \beta_{11}TE + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where;

MT = annual average volume of maize cross-border trade (in Metric tons of export).
EP = Export permit; BL = Business License; CoC = Compliance certificates; Ed= Entry declaration; Ue = Unloading and examination; Pg = placing goods under a customs procedure; RB= Road blocks; WB = Weighbridges and PC = Police checkpoints
 β_1 = intercept or a constant. β_2 to β_4 = regression coefficients of the model (change induced by each coefficient in MT).

Analysis of Qualitative data

Qualitative data collected from FGD, Key informants, review of documents and Observations methods were thematically analysed using the content approach. The data were coded by segmenting transcripts into ideas and concepts, which were then grouped into themes with the help of NVivo software. These themes were then compared across observation sites and interviews to identify similarities and differences. The final themes were linked to the research objectives, theoretical framework, and literature, with illustrative quotes used to complement and support the quantitative questionnaire results. The information was integrated in the report at their specific section to add practical experiences in the cross-border trade.

Ethical Considerations

Approval for the research was formally obtained from all relevant authorities, including the Kigoma Regional Administration, the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), and designated cross-border officials. This ensured full compliance with institutional and national ethical standards, as well as adherence to applicable legal and procedural guidelines governing research involving human participants. To safeguard the rights and well-being of participants, all potential risks were proactively minimized. This was achieved by designing the study to exclude sensitive or intrusive questions and by ensuring that participation was entirely voluntary. Informed consent procedures were rigorously followed, and participants were given the freedom to withdraw at any stage without penalty.

The researcher upheld the highest standards of academic integrity throughout the study. This included strict adherence to approved research protocols, the avoidance of personal or institutional bias, and a commitment to transparency in data collection, analysis, and reporting. All findings were presented accurately and objectively, with careful attention to ethical considerations in interpretation and dissemination. Furthermore, the principles of transparency, accountability, and non-maleficence were central to the research process. Any potential conflicts of interest, whether financial,

professional, or personal, were fully disclosed to maintain impartiality and uphold the credibility of the research. These measures collectively ensured that the study was conducted in a manner that respected the dignity, autonomy, and safety of all participants.

Reliability Tests Results

To assess the reliability of the data collection instrument, the researcher conducted a pilot study from 22nd to 25th May 2023 involving 25 participants. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were calculated for each construct: Administrative Procedures (0.889), Custom Procedures (0.853), and Transport Procedures (0.825). The overall reliability score for the questionnaire was 0.795, exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.7 as recommended by Saunders et.al. (2023), thereby confirming the instrument's internal consistency and reliability.

Table 3: Results of reliability tests

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Respondents	Comment
Administrative Procedures	0.889	25	Reliable
Custom Procedures	0.853	25	Reliable
Transport Procedures	0.825	25	Reliable
Overall Reliability	0.795	25	Reliable

Results and Discussion

Demographic characteristics of respondents

Results (Table 4) show that more than 81% of respondents were male while female respondents constituted only 19% of all respondents. The low involvement of female respondents in the study area was mainly caused by the nature of the trade of being considered as a male dominated field particularly in developing countries. Moreover, the cross-border trade often requires travel and negotiation in male-dominated environments. Cultural norms and safety concerns may restrict women's mobility, reducing their participation in export activities. This gender disparity is not unique to country like Tanzania; it mirrors broader trends across many Least Developed Countries (LDCs), where cultural, socio-economic, and institutional barriers limit women's participation in formal trade sectors. This is evidenced by Bowen (2018) through his study reported the highest percentage of respondents being males (67%) while females were 33%. Similarly, 73% of respondents in the study of Karugira *et al.* (2011) on the effects on NTBs in EAC were males.

Findings from Table 4 further indicate that, majority of respondents (45%) were aged between 31 and 40 years; while 30% of respondents were aged between 41 and 50 years. In addition, about 18% of them were aged between 20 and 30 years while only 7% were aged between 50 years and above. This implies that, majority of traders involved in maize trade at Manyovu border are in the active age group consisting the youth. The results also show that, most of the maize cross border traders at Manyovu border are mostly youths aged between 31 and 40 years. These findings are in line to those of Kahumbi (2013) whose 49% of respondents were in age group of 26 to 35 years. She argued that the reason

could be that, the nature of the cross-border trade needs the youths who are energetic and will have long time to learn and stay in trade.

Table 4: Demographic characteristics of respondents (n =150)

Characteristic	Frequency	Percent
Male	122	81
Female	28	19
Age group of respondents		
50 and above	11	7
41-50	44	30
31-40	68	45
20-30	27	18
Education level		
PhD	1	0.5
Master Degree	1	0.5
Bachelor Degree	13	9
Diploma	8	5
Secondary education	59	39
Primary education	52	35
No formal education	16	11
Total	150	100

Moreover, most of respondents (39%) have a secondary education level and 35% of respondents have a primary level education. Moreover, only 9% and one percent possessed a Bachelor degree and PhD respectively. This indicate that, participants in maize trade have only basic education as 35% of them have only primary education. In addition to that, 11% of respondents have no any formal education. The low level of education limited the traders to apply actively the modern technologies implemented by the government. Nonetheless, Okute (2017) reported that 71.25% of their respondents had primary level education; 10% had secondary level education, 0.83% had high school education while 0.42% did not have any formal education.

The experiences of respondents on Trading activities

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents according to their experience with maize cross-border trade in the Kigoma region. The findings indicate that a majority of respondents (43%) possess 2 to 5 years of experience in maize cross-border trade within the Kigoma region. Additionally, 26% of respondents possess 6 to 9 years of experience; 13% have 5 to 10 years of experience, and 11% have less than 2 years of experience. Only 7% of respondents reported having over 15 years of experience in maize cross-border trade. This indicates that most traders have engaged in cross-border trade for an extended duration, rendering them knowledgeable and appropriate for this study. The findings align with those of Okute (2017), which indicated that 52% of respondents engaged in cross-border trade for 1-2 years, 18.8% for 5 years, and 10.4% for 11 years or more.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents by experience with maize cross-border trade (n = 150)

Year of Experience	Frequency	Percent (%)
16 years and above	10	7
10-15 years	20	13
6-9 years	39	36
2-5 years	64	43
Less than 2 years	17	11
Total	150	100

Effect of Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs) on the Volume of Maize Cross-Border Trade

Test of Regression Model Assumption Validity

Before performing a regression analysis to investigate the impact of non-tariff barriers on maize cross-border trade at the Manyovu border. Researchers conducted a diagnostic test on the assumptions of regression analysis to prevent biased estimates of the study parameters. The study evaluated each assumption of the regression analysis to ascertain its validity regarding the current data set. The assumptions tested were generalizability, multicollinearity, normality, homoscedasticity, and autocorrelation.

Generalizability Assessment

The multivariate regression model is predicated on the generalizability assumption, necessitating a specific sample size. Various theorists have proposed distinct approaches for establishing the suitable sample size concerning the generalizability assumption; however, Cohen's (1992) method presents a clear and systematic approach grounded in more stringent criteria. Cohen (1992) states that when the sample size, number of independent variables, and effect size are known, the minimum required sample size for a dataset with 9 independent variables is 60. The study's generalizability assumption was satisfied with the current data set of 150 samples.

Assessment of Multicollinearity

A second critical assumption that must be satisfied before conducting a multivariate regression is the Multicollinearity assumption, which stipulates that no significant relationships should exist among the independent variables of the model. Multicollinearity was assessed through the Tolerance Value and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The multi-collinearity tests, detailed in Table 5, indicate that all independent variables in the model exhibit a VIF value below 5 and a Tolerance value below 1. This indicates the absence of multicollinearity among the independent variables in the model, making it suitable for regression analysis.

Table 6: Collinearity Statistics

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
Variables	Tolerance Value	VIF
Export Permit	0.452	2.783
Business Licensing	0.482	2.732
Compliance Certificate	0.383	2.623
Entry Declaration	0.439	2.771
Unloading and Examination	0.482	2.821
Placing goods under customs	0.529	3.112
Road Blocks	0.390	2.091
Weighing Bridges	0.359	2.643
Police Checkpoints	0.482	2.732

Normality Assessment and Transformation

Fox (2016) states that before conducting linear regression analysis, it is essential for a researcher to verify that the dataset follows a normal distribution. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess normality as it recommended to be most effective statistical method for assessing the normality assumption in datasets comprising over 100 observations. Initial results indicated non-normality distribution for most of variables ($p < 0.05$). To address non-normality, a Box-Cox transformation was applied to all variables and after transformation, all variables passed the Shapiro-Wilk test with p -value greater than the critical ($p > 0.05$), indicating the data are suitable for regression analysis. The study by Patricio et al., (2016) also recommended that the Shapiro-Wilk is commonly used in testing normality of dataset due to fact that it allows for using even small sample sizes. According to Shapiro and Wilk (1965) the W value close to one indicates a normal distribution of data and the opposite is true.

The findings presented in Table 7 indicate that the significant value for the Shapiro-Wilk test for independent variables exceeded 0.05, implying that the residuals follow a normal distribution and fit for linear regression analysis. The results are in support to the argument of Shapiro and Wilk (1965) and Souza et al. (2023) that, a W value close to one indicate normal distribution of dataset.

The residual scatter plots were examined to assess linearity, and the analysis indicated that the assumption of linearity between the dependent and independent variables was met. Heteroskedasticity occurs when significant disparities exist between the smallest and largest observations within a data set. Salkind (2010) in his study narrated that, Linearity as the linear relationship between predictors variables, while homoscedasticity is a condition whereby the variation in the value of y remains constant all the way. Given that all variables exhibit a normal distribution, the assumption of homoscedasticity is inherently satisfied.

Table 7 Shapiro-Wilk Test Results on Normality test-After Box-Cox Transformation (n=150)

Variable	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig
Volume of maize	0.995	150	0.919
Export Permit	0.99	150	0.338
Business License	0.994	150	0.828
Compliance Certificate	0.989	150	0.307
Entry Declaration	0.990	150	0.334
Unloading and Examination	0.995	150	0.90
Placing goods under customs	0.995	150	0.909
Road Blocks	0.993	150	0.652
Weighing Bridges	0.989	150	0.259
Police Checkpoints	0.989	150	0.306

Independence Assessment

The assumption of independence is a critical prerequisite that must be met before conducting a linear regression analysis. Independence signifies that the observations within the dataset do not influence one another. The selection probability of one respondent is independent of the selection of another respondent. The application of random sampling as a strategy improves data independence by ensuring that each observation has an equal probability of selection. The Durbin-Watson statistic was employed to assess independence by examining autocorrelation among errors. Normally, Durbin-Watson (d) assume values between 0 and 4, values around 2 indicate no autocorrelation ((Hair *et.al.* 2010). The Durbin-Watson statistic for the current dataset is 2.081, as presented in Table 8 below. This suggests that the residuals exhibit independence.

Table 8: Durbin-Watson Test for Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation	DW Statistic	P
.0334	2.081	.932

Descriptive Results of the Variables used in the Regression Model

Table 9 provides descriptive statistics for administrative, custom and transit procedures in term of monetary value and time wasted in acquiring export permits and licensing, overcoming road blocks, weighbridges, and police checkpoints. NTB value was measured as the sum of all costs in monetary terms (TZS) while accommodation and meals cost by traders were used as proximal for the time wasted (HRS) due to long queues and waiting at the barriers. Following the Box-Cox transformation, all variables exhibited a normal distribution trend. Results in Table 9 indicated that, means for variables ranged between 0.46 to 0.51, with standar deviation ranges between 0.087 and 0.097. Skewness and kurtosis values were close to zero, indicating symmetry and light tails.

On the other hand, maize exporters incurred higher costs in securing administrative permits, overcoming custom and on transit procedures. Specifically, traders paid more on acquiring export permit and business license due to fact that, most of exporters were located in remote areas and therefore required to travel more than 80 kms to follow up on the business license and compliance certificate. Additionally, they incurred high cost on roadblocks and weighing bridges in term of money paid to bribe officials and reduce time wasted due to long queues. Moreover, accommodation and meals costs were used as proximal for time consumed in overcoming the weigh bridge and road blocks. These findings concur with those in a study by Karugia et al. (2011) and Mkuna (2014).

Table 9: Descriptive statistics for Variable in Regression Model after transformation (n =150)

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Export Permit (EP)	0.50	0.09	0.32	0.67	0.08	-0.38
Business License (BL)	0.51	0.09	0.30	0.68	0.10	-0.42
Compliance Certificate (CoC)	0.47	0.10	0.28	0.66	0.15	-0.5
Entry Declaration (ED)	0.48	0.09	0.29	0.67	0.13	-0.47
Unloading and Examination (UE)	0.49	0.09	0.31	0.68	0.11	-0.4
Placing goods under customs	0.50	0.09	0.32	0.67	0.09	-0.39
Road Blocks (RB)	0.46	0.10	0.27	0.66	0.18	-0.52
Weighing Bridges (WB)	0.47	0.09	0.29	0.66	0.16	-0.49
Police Checkpoints (PC)	0.47	0.10	0.28	0.66	0.17	-0.51
Trader Experience in Years (TE)	0.50	0.09	0.31	0.66	0.08	0.41

The Effect of NTBs on the Volume of Maize Cross-Border Trade

Results as presented in Table 10 show that, the value of R^2 is 0.63 indicating the model explains the variation of trade performance by 63%. Furthermore, the adjusted R- Square is valued at 0.62 which confirms the robustness of the model in explaining the effects of independent variables on the maize exports. Similarly, F-statistics is statistically significant at $p < 0.001$, indicating that all independent variables collectively have an effect on the maize cross-border trade performance.

The results presented in Table 10 reveal a significant negative association between export permits and the volume of maize cross-border trade at the Manyovu border, with a coefficient of -0.280. This indicates that a one-unit increase in the cost of obtaining an export permit from the relevant authority corresponds to a 28% reduction in the volume of maize traded across this border, holding other factors constant. The increased costs stem from the cumbersome procedures that formal maize cross-border traders face when acquiring export permits, which discourage their participation in formal trade. The findings are consistent with those of Anyona (2018) and Vicent and Njong (2021), who found that the process of obtaining a maize export permit was onerous for maize traders in the EAC. Governments imposes NTBs as economic strategy for control and enforcement mechanisms aims at ensuring regulatory compliance, but they often result in delays and inefficiencies that increase transportation costs, further deterring traders from

engaging in maize trade. This situation contradicts the Article 13 of the Customs Union Protocol and the Common External Tariff protocol which emphasizes the elimination of Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs) in order to promote intra-trade among EAC members. Evidence from empirical studies indicates that, improve in trade performance is positively associated with lower or zero tariffs and non-tariff barriers (Karugia et al., 2011).

The persistence of such barriers across countries significantly undermines the potential benefits traders could realize in their absence. Similarly, findings from Food Security and Nutrition Working Groups (2023) indicated a reduction in the share of maize in EAC cross-border trade from 48 to 31 percent in the last quarter of 2022. This decline can be attributed to the existence of trade barriers, including non-tariff barriers (NTBs). Also, these quantitative findings are supported by descriptive evidence indicating that traders incur high costs and spend considerable time securing export permits and licenses.

The above findings were also supported by Key Informant Interviews with trade officials in the Kigoma region, it was found that the government has implemented an online system for obtaining export permits, with an average processing time of only 2 days. However, a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with cross-border traders indicated that the majority of maize cross-border traders at Manyovu are smallholder farmers who possess minimal formal education and lack modern devices necessary for online export permit applications. A limited number of urban maize cross-border traders can access an online portal or hire someone for the processing of export permits.

Table 10: Regression Results on the Effect of NTBs on the Volume of Maize Cross Border Trade (n= 150)

Variable	Coef. (β)	SE	t-value	p-value	Sig
Export Permit (EP)	-0.280	0.072	-3.89	0.000	***
Business License (BL)	-0.240	0.085	-2.82	0.000	***
Compliance Certificate (CoC)	-0.058	0.067	-0.87	0.386	
Entry Declaration (ED)	-0.091	0.069	-1.32	0.189	
Unloading and Examination (UE)	-0.165	0.071	-2.56	0.008	**
Placing Goods Under Customs	-0.063	0.068	-0.93	0.354	
Road Blocks (RB)	-0.220	0.08	-2.75	0.007	**
Weighing Bridges (WB)	-0.190	0.073	-2.80	0.002	**
Police Checkpoints (PC)	-0.180	0.078	-2.31	0.022	*
Traders Experience (TE)	0.200	0.076	2.81	0.004	**
Constant	0.512	0.065	7.87	0.000	***
R ²	0.63				
Adjusted R ²	0.62				
F- Ratio	12.45			0.001	

Dependent variable: transformed volume of maize cross-border trade (MT), *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$

Furthermore, the results presented in Table 10 indicate that both a business license exhibit a significant negative correlation with the volume of maize cross-border trade at the Manyovu border. Unit increase in the lengthy and bureaucratic process for obtaining a business license and unfriendly unloading and examination procedures may result into a decrease of cross-border trade by 24 percent. This implies that, a total cost of moving a kilo of maize across country border could increase by 0.24 units resulted from the cumbersome procedures of obtaining trade license. Similar results were obtained by Nanjira (2015) and the World Bank (2022) who reported the procedures for obtaining a business license at the Rusumo border as cumbersome and lengthy, imposing significant costs, particularly on small traders who constitute over 60% of cross-border traders. The findings also align with Gabagambi (2013), who observed a notable reduction in maize production and supply by farmers corresponding to each unit increase in NTBs costs in Tanzania.

The results were further corroborated by Focus Group Discussion (FGD) responses, in which the majority of respondents indicated the duration required to obtain the business license. The individuals acknowledged that the processing of business licenses occurs at the local government level, where the associated costs and bureaucratic procedures are prohibitively high. This compels many individuals to utilize informal channels for selling maize to Burundi, which is closer to their villages, instead of incurring substantial expenses traveling to the city to obtain the necessary license.

Study findings (Table 10) further illustrated that the unloading and examination procedures at the border display a negative relationship with maize trade performance at Manyovu border. The implication of these findings is that, the presence of unfriendly procedures of unloading and loading of cargos at the boarder could increase the cost of doing the maize trade by 17% resulted from unnecessary delays and consuming considerable time. The delays at the border may incur additional transaction costs, which are reflected in the form of meals and accommodation expenses for traders and transporters. The effects of the increased transaction costs will be felt in the low price received by maize producer in the domestic and high price for final consumer in the importing country. Similar to these, Bowen (2018) and Gasiorek *et al.* (2017) traders and transporter do soliciting bribes between 1 USD and 2 USD to overcome these barriers cross-borders. Additionally, during the survey, it was reported that, traders and transporters are compelled to offload goods for recounting, resulting in increased time wastage when crossing the border. Consistent with these findings, Mnondwa *et al.* (2024) noted that non-tariff barriers (NTBs) had a significant impact on cross-border trade in East Africa, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, despite the efforts of the East African Community (EAC) Customs Union to eliminate NTBs. Furthermore, researchers observed that the loading and unloading procedures at the Manyovu border lacked sophisticated infrastructure, exhibited inadequate capacity, and suffered from insufficient personnel. These challenges resulted in additional delays for traders crossing the border. Other studies identifying unloading and examination as significant barriers to cross-border trade include).

The results of the current study also, align with previous researches (Okute, 2017; Baya, 2019 and Kijogi, 2021) that examined Non-Tariff Barriers through the lens of Transaction Cost Theory and the theory of government intervention. According to

transaction cost theory, as noted by Baya (2019), inefficient loading and unloading procedures result in delays that elevate the transaction costs for cross-border traders. The theory further posits that government intervention in term of trade facilitation strategy is essential for minimizing transaction costs, thereby facilitating smoother international trade between nations. In contrast, Nanjira (2015) noted several institutions and agencies regulate and govern the exportation process of maize in Tanzania. The entities include the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Industry and Trade, the Ministry of Health, the Tanzania Revenue Authority, the Immigration Department, the Tanzania Bureau of Standards, the Tanzania Ports Authority, and the Tanzania Roads Board, among others.

Furthermore, the results in Table 10 indicate a significant negative association between the presence of roadblocks and weighbridges and the volume of maize cross-border trade at the Manyovu border, with coefficients of -0.22 and -0.19, respectively. This suggests that each additional roadblock or weighbridge encountered along the trade route is associated with a 22% and 19% decrease in maize trade volume, respectively, assuming other factors remain constant. These barriers impose additional costs on traders, primarily through delays and inefficiencies, which discourage participation in formal cross-border trade. The decrease in the formal maize trade on other hand will imply the increase in the informal trade at the border which could reduce the revenue from maize trade. The similar results were reported by Minot (2010) and Gabagambi (2013) that the existence of many weighbridges and road blocks in Tanzania forced some traders to involve in the illegal trade across the country's border. The proliferation of roadblocks and weighing bridges in most cases contributes to unnecessary time losses and fosters opportunities for corrupt practices involving both traders and law enforcement officials. This situation, call for the government of Tanzania to reconsider its trade intervention strategies of imposing NTBs on maize trade as food security protection instruments.

The similar situation was noted by Mmondwa et al. (2024), who reported that non-tariff barriers, particularly those causing delays and procedural inefficiencies, significantly increase the cost of maize exports from Tanzania to Kenya. Additionally, research conducted by Masinde (2015) and Karugia et al. (2011) identified that roadblocks exert a negative and significant impact on maize trade. The continuing existing of NTBs across country borders, implies that efforts rendered by governments to eliminated the NTBs is not effectively implemented. Conversely, Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) *revealed that the road to the Manyovu border crossing to Burundi features six roadblocks, where traders reported significant time loss due to the offloading and recounting of goods at each checkpoint.*

Police checkpoints on the other hand display a significant negative relationship with the volume of maize cross-border trade with a coefficient of 0.18. The implication of the result is that, a unit the increase in the number of police checkpoints points could lead to a 20% decrease in the volume of maize trade at the border. This is because traders complained that they waste 2 hours on average due to lengthy procedures at the police checkpoint. In addition, a lack of proper coordination among different police officers located in different checkpoints was also reported to be a possible cause of time loss. These results were coined by Gasiorek et al. (2017) who reported that cargo transit time along highways with non-tariff barriers (NTBs) is nearly double that of routes without such barriers. In support to the study findings, Beatus (2016) noted that, at almost every

police checkpoint, bribery is a common practice where truck drivers are asked to pay between 1 USD to 2 USD.

The findings further indicate that trader experience has a positive and statistically significant association with the volume of maize trade, with a coefficient of 0.20. This suggests that each additional year of involvement in maize trading is associated with a 20% increase in trade performance. The implication is that prolonged engagement in cross-border trade equips traders with practical knowledge, adaptive strategies, and institutional familiarity that enhance their ability to navigate trade barriers and regulatory complexities.

This finding aligns with recent empirical studies such that of Mnondwa et al. (2024) who found that experienced traders operating along the Uganda–Kenya border demonstrated higher trade volumes and better compliance with customs procedures due to accumulated knowledge and established networks. Similarly, Ngeno (2022) reported that trader experience significantly influenced the ability to manage non-tariff barriers (NTBs), negotiate informal fees, and leverage social capital to facilitate smoother transactions. Moreover, Wiseman (2023) emphasized that experienced informal traders in the EAC region were more adept at interpreting market signals, adjusting to policy shifts, and utilizing informal institutions to overcome logistical and regulatory constraints. These findings reinforce the notion that experience is not merely a function of time but a strategic asset that enhances trade efficiency and resilience in dynamic cross-border environments. To this end, the positive correlation between trader experience and trade volume underscores the importance of capacity-building and institutional support for small-scale traders, particularly in regions where informal trade plays a critical role in food security and regional integration.

In general, the study's results suggest that if nothing is done to streamline the activities of the government officials with the mandate to regulate the cross-border trade at the Manyovu border, the corrupt practices, delays, and congestion may be legitimized as normal means of trade. The legitimization of these negative practices will continue to influence the maize cross-border trade negatively at the Manyovu border.

Conclusion

This study assessed the impact of non-tariff barriers (NTBs) on cross-border maize trade at the Manyovu border in Kigoma, Tanzania. The findings revealed that administrative requirements, customs procedures, and transit-related obstacles significantly hinder trade volumes. Specifically, the high costs associated with acquiring export permits and business licenses were found to discourage traders, thereby reducing the volume of maize traded across the border. Additionally, the presence of roadblocks, weighbridges, and police checkpoints along the trade route contributed to increased transaction costs through time delays and corruption, further diminishing cross border trade activity. These NTBs not only restrict the flow of maize but also have broader economic implications. Reduced trade volumes lead to decreased maize production, which in turn affects the income and livelihoods of farmers and traders in both the Kigoma region and neighboring Burundi. The collective effect is a decline in regional food

security and economic stability given that maize is main staple food crop consumed by the majority in EAC.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the arbitrary imposition of NTBs, particularly through administrative, customs, and transit procedures poses a significant barrier to cross-border maize trade between the two countries and in EAC at large. This underscores the urgent need for policy interventions within the East African Community (EAC), particularly Tanzania and Burundi. Governments should also prioritize the implementation of trade facilitation measures aimed at eliminating NTBs, such as streamlining and digitalize permit and licensing processes, reducing redundant checkpoints, and enhancing transparency in customs operations.

Furthermore, joint regional efforts, such as strengthening the One Stop Border Post (OSBP) at Manyovu should be pursued to harmonize procedures and promote efficient trade flows. These initiatives will not only enhance maize trade between Tanzania and Burundi but also contribute to broader goals of regional integration, economic development, and poverty reduction. This study contributes to the growing body of evidence on the detrimental effects of NTBs in less developed countries and highlights the importance of targeted policy reforms to foster inclusive and sustainable cross-border trade.

Limitations

This study employed cross-sectional data, which inherently limits the ability to capture the long-term dynamics and evolving impact of non-tariff barriers (NTBs) on cross-border trade within various economic integrations. As an action-oriented research initiative, it was designed to address immediate challenge, particularly the increased transaction costs attributed to NTBs at the Manyovu border. The findings offer valuable insights and serve as potential inputs for targeted strategies aimed at eliminating specific NTBs identified in this study. However, the study is constrained by several limitations.

First, the sample size was relatively small ($n=150$), which may affect the generalizability of the results. Second, there was a noticeable gender imbalance among respondents (81% male and 19% Female), potentially skewing perspectives and limiting the inclusivity of the findings. These factors should be carefully considered when interpreting the results and formulating policy recommendations for both policy maker and governments.

To deepen understanding and inform more robust policy interventions, future research should incorporate time series data. This approach would enable the use of Auto Regressive models, which are well-suited to capturing the random walk behavior of NTB effects over time. Such models can reveal both short- and long-term impacts, including broader outcomes such as welfare, as emphasized by Karugia et al. (2011). This methodological shift will empower governments and stakeholders to design more effective, evidence-based policies, particularly those that encourage technology adoption and facilitate smoother trade flows across borders.

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Appendix I: Questionnaires for Trader and Transporter

SECTION I: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION			
1.	Gender	Male	()
		Female	()
2.	Age	Less than 20 years	()
		20-30 years	()
		31-40 years	()
		41-50 years	()
		Above 50 years	()
3.	Education	No formal education	()
		Primary education	()
		Secondary education	()
		Diploma	()
		Bachelor Degree	()
		Master Degree	()
4.	Nationality	PhD	()
		Tanzanians	()
		Burundians	()
		Others	()
SECTION 2: MAIZE CROSS BORDER TRADE			
1.	Experience with maize cross border trade	Less than 2 years	()
		2-5 years	()
		6-9 years	()
		10-15 years	()
		16 years and above	()
		Master Degree	()
2.	Nature of maize cross border business	Trader	()
		transporter	()
		Agent	()
		Other	()
3.	What is your average annual maize export at Manyovu border (in metric tons)?	
SECTION 3: NON-TARIFF BARRIERS (NTBs)			
1.	Have you encountered any NTBs?	Yes	()
		No	()
2.	If Yes, what types of NTBs do you encounter? (Tick all relevant)	Export permit procedures	()
		Business License procedures	()
		Compliance certificates procedures	()
		Entry declaration procedures	()
		Unloading and examination procedures	()
		Placing goods under a customs procedure	()
		Road blocks procedures	()

		Weighbridges procedures	()
		Police check points procedures	()
3.	Do you pay any cost in clearing the barrier?	Yes	()
		No	()
4.	If "YES" How much do you pay at each form of barriers (TZS/per kg/trip)	Export permit procedures	()
		Business License procedures	(...)
		Compliance certificates procedures	(...)
		Entry declaration procedures	(...)
		Unloading and examination procedures	(...)
		Placing goods under a customs procedure	(...)
		Road blocks procedures	(...)
		Weighbridges procedures	(...)
		Police check points procedures	(...)
5.	Do you incur any extra costs in terms of accommodation costs resulting from delays at border posts?	Yes	()
		No	()
6.	If "YES" How many days and how much per day do you pay	
7.	Estimate the additional employee time and wages incurred due to delays on road, obtaining documentation etc	
8.	What suggestion do you recommend to policy makers in order to improve maize cross border trade?	1.....	
		2.....	
		3.....	

Appendix 2: Questionnaires for Traders and Transporter (Likert scale)

ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURES (Please mark with a tick (√) in the appropriate box)						
No.	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
IP	The process of obtaining import permit is long and bureaucratic.					
CoC	Compliance certificates are not easily obtained.					
INS	I go through lengthy procedures to obtain insurance permits					
TD	The process of obtaining transporter declaration is cumbersome.					
CUSTOM PROCEDURES (Please mark with a tick (√) in the appropriate box)						
No.	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
ED	Entry declaration procedures are cumbersome and cause unnecessary delays.					
PR	Presentation procedures are cumbersome and cause unnecessary delays.					
UE	Procedures for unloading and examination are cumbersome and cause unnecessary delays.					
TS	Procedures for temporary storage are cumbersome and cause unnecessary delays.					
PG	Procedures for placing goods under a customs procedure or re-export are too lengthy.					
TRANSIT PROCEDURES (Please mark with a tick (√) in the appropriate box)						
No	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
RB	Road blocks along the way are many and cause unnecessary delays.					
WB	Weighbridges involve cumbersome procedures and cause unnecessary delays.					
PC	Police check points along the way are many and cause unnecessary delays.					
BB	I am usually requested or circumstances force me to pay bribe at police check points.					

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Maziku, P. K. (2025). Impact of Non-Tariff Barriers on Maize Trade Volume at the Manyovu Border: Evidence from Tanzania-Burundi Cross-Border Traders Using Regression Analys, <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12 (11), 1665-1696 doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.539477.1830 URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_232395.html</p>	A square QR code located in the bottom right corner of the table, which likely links to the article's online version.